

A New Chelating Material Prepared by Modification of an Anion Exchanger

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A new chelating material, titanium(IV) diethanolamine, has been prepared by modification of hydrous titanium oxide. This material possesses a metal sorption capacity of 0.6 to 0.9 m mole g⁻¹, and shows selective retention of certain metal ions. It has been found useful for the analytical separation of Cd(II) from Pb(II), Cu(II) and Hg(II); Th(IV) from Hg(II) and Mn(II) from Fe(III). The rate of sorption has also been determined.

MOST inorganic ion exchangers reported so far have been prepared by mixing quadrivalent metal ions with salts of group V and VI elements¹⁻³. Hydroxides of polyvalent metals such as zirconium and thorium oxide⁴⁻⁵ have been found to behave as anion as well as cation exchangers. The use of some organic compounds capable of forming complexes with various metal ions has been restricted to only organic resins⁶. Pyridinium tungstoarsenate⁷ and amine-tin hexacyanoferrate⁸ are the only inorganic ion exchangers which incorporate such groups in their frame work. These exchangers, however, exhibit only the cation exchange properties. In an attempt to prepare inorganic chelating materials, we successfully introduced diethanolamine group into the frame work of Sn(IV) oxide⁹. This material, stannic-diethanolamine, showed selective sorption for different metal ions depending on their stability constants with diethanol amine. In the present studies, the synthesis of a new chelating material, titanium-diethanolamine, is reported. Its behaviour towards various metal ions and its use for the separation of some metal ions have also been studied.

Experimental

Titanium(IV) chloride (B.D.H.) and diethanolamine (B.D.H.) were used for the preparation of the

exchanger. All other chemicals were of analytical grade.

0.3% solution of Cu(II), Fe(III), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Co(II), Hg(II), Th(IV), Pb(II) and Mg(II) were prepared by dissolving their nitrates in demineralized water.

Synthesis: 0.1 M solution of Ti(IV) chloride was mixed with 0.5 M solution of diethanolamine in the volume ratios shown in Table 1. The mixture was left overnight at room temp. to ensure complete precipitation. The white precipitate so obtained was filtered, washed with deionized water and dried at 45 ± 5° in an oven. The dried product was allowed to cool completely before it was washed again with deionized water; if washed while hot, the material shows strong tendency to hydrolyse. The material was then redried in the oven at 40°.

The sample S₃ was prepared by homogeneous precipitation method in which Ti(IV) was initially masked with hydrogen peroxide and diethanolamine was then added. The flask containing the above reaction mixture was placed on a waterbath for evaporation and decomposition of hydrogen peroxide which released Ti(V) slowly to react with the amine.

Sorption capacity: 0.5 g of the exchanger was shaken with 2 ml 0.01 M metal ion solution in a

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS OF PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF TITANIUM DIETHANOLAMINE

Samples	Conditions of synthesis			Nature of precipitation	Properties	
	Molarity of reagents		Mixing volume ratio		Sorption capacity (m mole/g)	Ion-exchange capacity (m mole/g)
	Ti(IV) chloride	Diethanolamine				
S ₁	0.1 M	0.1 M	1 : 1	Precipitate appears but dissolved	—	—
S ₂	0.1 M	0.2 M	1 : 2	—do—	—	—
S ₃	0.2 M	0.1 M	2 : 1	—do—	—	—
S ₄	0.1 M	0.5 M	1 : 5	A thick precipitate	0.69	Nil

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conical flask containing 23 ml sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer (pH 6). After being shaken for 6 hr at room temp. the mixture was decanted and the amount of metal ion remaining in the filtrate was determined by chelometric titration.

Stability: 0.5 g of the exchanger was shaken in a conical flask for 4 hr in the solutions in which its dissolution was to be checked. The supernate was decanted and titanium(IV) was determined spectrophotometrically with H_2SO_4 and H_2O_2 methods. Diethanolamine was determined colorimetrically by sodium nitroprusside method¹⁰.

Composition: To determine titanium, a 0.5 g sample of titanium diethanolamine was dissolved in hydrofluoric acid and diluted to 50 ml with deionized water. Ti(IV) in this solution was determined spectrophotometrically. For the determination of diethanolamine, another 0.5 g sample was treated with 30 ml conc. H_2SO_4 in a Kjaldahl flask. The mixture was heated for about 30 min after which a small amount of potassium sulphate was added to catalyse the reaction. The mixture was boiled till it gave a clear solution indicating complete conversion of nitrogen into ammonium sulphate. The liquid so obtained was kept with 10 M NaOH and the released amine was trapped in a known quantity of hydrochloric acid. The amount of amine present in the exchanger was then calculated.

Breakthrough capacity: The breakthrough capacity was determined by column operation. Solutions of copper(II) nitrate containing 5 and 3 mg per bed volume of Cu(II) were passed through a column loaded with 1 g of the exchanger on a glass wool support. The flow rate was adjusted to 0.5 ml min^{-1} . The amount of Cu(II) in each fraction collected was determined.

Sorption of metal ions at different pH: To a glass stoppered conical flask containing 0.5 g dried exchanger and 23 ml 0.25 M HCl-0.25 M sodium acetate solutions (pH 1-6), 2 ml 0.01 M metal ion solutions was added. The mixture was then shaken for 6 hr at room temp. The supernatant was drained off and the amount of metal ion remaining in it was determined by chelometric titration.

Separations: Separations were carried out on 30 cm \times 0.39 cm² glass columns. 2 g Ti(IV)-diethanolamine was taken on a glass wool support of a column and washed with a pH 6 buffer solution. The mixtures of the metal ions to be separated were then allowed to trickle down the column at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min^{-1} .

Rate of sorption: The rate of sorption of Cu(II) ions on titanium(IV)-diethanolamine was determined by shaking 0.35 m mole of Cu(II) in solution with 0.5 g of the material for different intervals of time. The amount of unadsorbed ion was then determined in the supernatant.

Results and Discussion

The results of Table 1 show that precipitation of titanium-diethanolamine occurs when the amine

is taken in excess (titanium : amine, 1 : 5). This sample was selected for further studies. The product, titanium-diethanolamine, does not show any cation exchange capacity for the simple reason that the material contains no negative charge on its matrix. A strong tendency for metal sorption was, however, observed. The behaviour may possibly be due to the presence of a lone pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom of the amine group allowing its chelation with different metal ions.

The results of sorption capacity are reported in Table 2. The sorption capacity varies from 0.66 to 0.9 m mole g^{-1} . The reason for variation in the sorption capacities could be attributed to incomplete complex formation of some of the metal ions at the pH at which the sorption studies were made. Fe(III) is known to form a very weak complex with nitrogen containing compounds and hence its sorption capacity is only 0.3 m mole g^{-1} . Table 3 shows the

TABLE 2—SORPTION CAPACITY FOR DIFFERENT METAL IONS

Sl. No.	Metal ion	Sorption capacity (m mole/g)
1.	Cu ²⁺	0.69
2.	Ni ²⁺	0.88
3.	Fe ³⁺	0.30
4.	Hg ²⁺	0.90
5.	Mg ²⁺	0.66

TABLE 3—SOLUBILITY OF TITANIUM-DIETHANOLAMINE

Solvent	Solubility (mg/25 ml)	
	Ti(IV)	Diethanolamine
DMW	0.00	0.00
HCl, 0.1 M	0.01	0.02
HCl, 0.5 M	0.05	0.08
HCl, 2 M	0.15	0.20
NaOH, 0.1 M	0.20	0.09
NaOH, 1 M	22.00	30.00
NH ₄ OH, 0.1 M	0.05	0.04
NH ₄ OH, 2 M	0.70	1.00
HNO ₃ , 1 M	0.25	0.40

results of the dissolution of the material in different solvents. The material can be utilized for separation of metal ions involving neutral solutions and dilute acids and bases.

The analysis of the sample reveals the following results.

Amount of chelating material taken	= 0.5 g
Amount of diethanolamine found	= 99 mg
Amount of Ti(IV) found	= 54 mg

Therefore, the Ti : diethanolamine ratio in titanium-diethanolamine is approximately 1 : 2.

The results of breakthrough capacity of Cu(II) at two different concentrations are shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that up to 50 bed volumes can be safely passed through 1 g exchanger without detecting any Cu(II) ion in the effluent. But when the concentration of Cu(II) in the solution was increased breakthrough occurred almost immediately.

Fig. 1. Breakthrough capacity of titanium diethanolamine.

The sorption behaviour of 11 metal ions at different pH values are plotted in Fig. 2. Since the stability of the metal ligand complex depends upon the pH, change of pH of the equilibrating solution results in the variation in the extent of uptake of a metal ion. The figure illustrates the utility of the material for separation of certain metal ions. It can be seen that 1-4 is the most useful pH range for effecting such separations.

On the basis of large differences in sorptive ability of the metal ions at different pH, a number of

Fig. 2. Sorption of metal ions at different pH.

separations have been tried. Successful binary separations of Cd(II)-Pb(II), Cd(II)-Hg(II), Th(IV)-Hg(II), Cd(II)-Cu(II) and Mn(II)-Fe(III) have been achieved. The results of these separations are summarized in Table 4. The order of elution and eluents used are shown in Fig. 3a-e.

Fig. 3(a). Separation of Th(IV) - Hg(II).

Fig. 3(b). Separation of Cd(II) - Cu(II).

TABLE 4—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATIONS OF METAL IONS ON TITANIUM-DIETHANOLAMINE

Sl. No.	Separations	Eluents	Eluent volume ml	Amount loaded μ g	Amount found μ g
1.	Cd(II)	HCl + CH ₃ COONa, pH 4	80	501	509
	Pb(II)	HCl + CH ₃ COONa, pH 1	70	525	520
2.	Cd(II)	HCl + CH ₃ COONa, pH 4	60	495	501
	Hg(II)	HCl + CH ₃ COONa, pH 1	60	480	480
3.	Th(IV)	HCl + CH ₃ COONa, pH 2	60	510	509
	Hg(II)	HCl + CH ₃ COONa, pH 1	60	480	477
4.	Cd(II)	HCl + CH ₃ COONa, pH 4	60	500	506
	Cu(II)	HCl + CH ₃ COONa, pH 1	70	505	510
5.	Mn(II)	HCl + CH ₃ COONa, pH 5	60	512	503
	Fe(III)	HCl + CH ₃ COONa, pH 1	50	604	602

Fig. 3(c). Separation of Mn(II) - Fe(III).

Fig. 3(d). Separation of Cd(II) - Pb(II).

Fig. 3(e). Separation of Cd(II) - Hg(II).

Fig. 4 shows the result of the determination of rate of sorption of Cu(II). It reveals that only 50 min are required to reach the equilibrium. The equilibration rate in this case is faster than those on

Fig. 4. Rate of sorption of Cu(II).

inorganic ion-exchangers of zirconium phosphate type. It is, therefore, clear that the presence of amino group (a chelation site) is responsible for such a fast equilibration rate.

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